

Pediatric non-galenic pial arteriovenous fistula – particular endovascular management

Author: Ana Dobrin¹

Co-authors: Catherine Costan¹, Anastasia Sandu¹

Coordinator: Nicolaie Dobrin²

Affiliations:

¹ *University of Medicine and Pharmacy Gr.T.Popa Iasi*

² *Clinical Hospital of Neurosurgery Nicolaie Oblu Iasi*

Introduction

Pediatric non-galenic pial arteriovenous fistulas (pAVFs) are rare cerebrovascular malformations characterized by a direct pial arteriovenous connection and variable symptomatology. Early diagnosis and individualized management are crucial due to their typically poor natural history if left untreated, as well as their anatomical vascular peculiarities correlated with clinical manifestations. Endovascular treatment has emerged as a preferred option with promising outcomes.

Case Presentation

We report the case of a 3-years-old infant who presented with recurrent focal seizures, vomiting, orthostatic disturbances and progressive cognitive decline. Magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) and digital subtraction angiography (DSA) confirmed the presence of a cerebellar pAVF. Considering the age, the right femoral approach was performed under echographic guidance, then the 4F guidance system was inserted under biplane angiographic control. The radiological dosimetry parameters and contrast substance were continuously monitored. The technical difficulty consisted in the fact that the implants (microcoils) did not have stability at the fistula point due to high velocity flow, so it was decided to place a stent in the artery-venous fistulous point just near the venous varix dilation junction area. In this way, the anchoring of the microcoils implants was achieved much easier. Particular endovascular embolization technique achieved complete obliteration of the pAVF without any postprocedural complications. Clinical follow-up demonstrated a favorable neurological outcome.

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of early diagnosis using appropriate imaging and the need to adapt treatment to the specific vascular anatomy, especially in pediatric patients. Endovascular management represents an effective and safe treatment option for preventing life-threatening complications and achieving positive clinical outcomes in this rare condition.

Keywords

pediatric cerebrovascular, pial arteriovenous fistula, endovascular treatment